

DATA NEXUS

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org

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Colors

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or grey.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors.

Indigo Primary

#183568
R24 G53 B104
C77 M49 Y0 K59

Electric Blue Secondary

#57FFFF
R87 G255 B255
C66 M0 Y0 K0

White Neutral

#FFFFFF
R255 G255 B255
C0 M0 Y0 K0

Steel Blue Secondary

#3591AD
R53 G145 B173
C69 M16 Y0 K32

Black Neutral

#000000
R0 G0 B0
C60 M40 Y40 K100

Menthol Accent

#BEFF94
R190 G255 B148
C26 M0 Y42 K0

Blue-Gray Texts

#627089
R98 G112 B137
C28 M18 Y0 K46

Colors

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (grey or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

Gradient table

100%	100%	100%	100%
------	------	------	------

80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Aa

Titles

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

[Download here](#)

Oxanium Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789
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Typography

Paragraph
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Aa Bb

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Teachers Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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Mockups

DATA NEXUS

Title Example

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Title Example

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Title Example

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